

THE EFFECT OF LEADPRENEURSHIP AND COMPETENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE (SURVEY STUDY PT. JASA DAN KEPARIWISATAAN JAWA BARAT, TOUR AND TRAVEL UNIT)

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Abstract

PT. Jaswita Jabar, which is a Regionally-Owned Enterprise (BUMD) engaged in tourism, property and business services. PT. Jaswita Jabar has a vision to become the largest and most trusted property and tourism company in West Java in 2025. To achieve this vision, it is necessary to have a planned and structured business management so that PT. Jaswita Jabar is ready to compete in an increasingly competitive industrial world. The method used in this study is a quantitative approach, with descriptive and verification analysis. The research sample is employees in the PT. Jaswita Jabar environment. The results of the study using multiple linear regression analysis, obtained a regression equation model $Y = a + 0.835X_1 + 0.606X_2$, showing a positive direction coefficient, meaning that every change in leadpreneurship and competence will improve employee performance. While the results of the hypothesis test show a significant influence of leadpreneurship and competence on employee performance both partially and simultaneously, where the p-value.

Keywords: *leadership, employee competence, employee performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Business management in the property and tourism sectors plays a crucial role in optimizing economic potential, strengthening tourism attractiveness, and improving community welfare. West Java Province possesses abundant natural, cultural, historical, and infrastructural resources that are highly potential for development in both property and tourism sectors. One of the institutions responsible for managing these assets is PT. Jaswita Jabar, a Regional-Owned Enterprise (BUMD) engaged in tourism, property, and business services, which acts as an agent of development for the regional economy. To achieve its vision of becoming the largest and most trusted property and tourism company in West Java, PT. Jaswita Jabar requires well-planned and structured business management. A key determinant of organizational success is effective human resource management, as human resources serve as the foundation for optimal performance, continuous innovation, and adaptability to environmental changes. However, financial performance data over the past three years indicate fluctuations in assets and profits, suggesting that employee performance has not yet reached an optimal level. Preliminary surveys and observations reveal several performance-related issues among employees, including delays in task completion, inadequate communication, and a tendency to shift responsibilities to others. Employee performance is a vital factor for both individuals and organizations. Individually, performance influences career development and job satisfaction, while organizationally it determines productivity, competitiveness, and the achievement of strategic goals.

Table 1. Preliminary Survey Results on Employee Performance

No	Performance Aspect	Main Findings
1	Timeliness of task completion	Some employees fail to meet work deadlines consistently
2	Work coordination	Coordination exists but has not been fully effective
3	Information processing ability	Employees are generally capable of processing work-related information
4	Communication skills	Weaknesses remain in delivering information clearly and effectively
5	Teamwork	Information openness is perceived to improve teamwork

One important factor influencing employee performance is leadership. Entrepreneurial leadership, or leadpreneurship, integrates leadership capabilities with entrepreneurial values such as innovation, proactiveness, opportunity recognition, and adaptability. Preliminary findings indicate that although leadpreneurship has been perceived positively by employees at PT. Jaswita Jabar, its implementation remains inconsistent, particularly in fostering a sustainable culture of innovation. In addition to leadership, employee competence is another critical determinant of performance. Although the majority of employees hold undergraduate degrees, their competencies are not always aligned with the specific demands of the tourism industry. Furthermore, competency development through structured and continuous training programs is still limited. Inadequate competencies may hinder employees' ability to perform effectively and efficiently. Based on these conditions, it can be concluded that improving employee performance at PT. Jaswita Jabar requires both effective entrepreneurial leadership and appropriate employee competencies. Therefore, this study aims to examine the influence of entrepreneurial leadership and employee competence on employee performance at PT. Jasa dan Kepariwisata Jawa Barat, Tour and Travel Unit.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

Employee performance represents the degree to which employees successfully carry out their duties and responsibilities in accordance with organizational standards and objectives. Performance is not merely the final output of work, but also reflects the process through which tasks are completed, including efficiency, accuracy, timeliness, and the ability to collaborate effectively within the organization. In service-based organizations such as tourism and travel companies, employee performance is a critical determinant of service quality, customer satisfaction, and organizational sustainability. Mathis and Jackson (2011) define performance as the actions and behaviors that employees demonstrate in fulfilling their job responsibilities. This definition emphasizes that performance encompasses both what employees do and what they fail to do, indicating that neglect, delays, and ineffective work behaviors also form part of performance assessment. Mangkunegara (2017) further explains that performance is the result of work achieved by an employee in terms of quality and quantity, in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. High employee performance contributes directly to productivity, organizational effectiveness, and competitive advantage.

Employee performance is closely linked to organizational success because it serves as a measurable indicator of how well human resources are managed. Employees with high performance levels tend to show strong commitment, discipline, and initiative, which positively affect operational efficiency. Conversely, low performance may manifest in missed deadlines, weak coordination, poor communication, and suboptimal service delivery, which can hinder organizational growth. In the context of tourism and travel services, performance carries additional significance due to the direct interaction between employees and customers. Employees are required to demonstrate not only technical competence but also interpersonal skills, adaptability, and responsiveness. Effective performance ensures that services are delivered consistently, customer expectations are met, and the organization maintains a positive reputation. Based on the literature, employee performance can be measured through several key indicators. These indicators commonly include quality of work, quantity of work, timeliness in task completion, effectiveness in achieving work targets, and the ability to cooperate with others. These dimensions provide a comprehensive assessment of employee contributions to organizational objectives

Entrepreneurial Leadership (Leadpreneurship)

Entrepreneurial leadership, often referred to as leadpreneurship, is a leadership style that integrates traditional leadership functions with entrepreneurial characteristics such as innovation, opportunity recognition, proactiveness, and risk management. This leadership approach emphasizes the leader's role in driving organizational growth by encouraging creativity, adaptability, and value creation among employees.

Suharsaputra (2014) defines entrepreneurial leadership as leadership that applies entrepreneurial principles in guiding and influencing organizational members to achieve strategic goals. This form of leadership is particularly relevant in dynamic and competitive environments where organizations must continuously adapt to changes in market conditions, technology, and consumer preferences. Purhantara (as cited in Safuan, 2018) explains that entrepreneurial leadership focuses on the leader's ability to inspire innovation, anticipate change, and mobilize organizational resources effectively. Entrepreneurial leaders are characterized by their visionary mindset, which enables them to identify future opportunities and challenges. They do not merely direct employees to perform tasks but also provide meaning and purpose behind organizational goals. By communicating a clear vision, entrepreneurial leaders motivate employees to take ownership of their work and contribute proactively to organizational success.

Entrepreneurial leadership promotes an organizational culture that supports innovation and learning. Leaders who practice leadpreneurship encourage employees to share ideas, experiment with new approaches, and view challenges as opportunities for improvement. This leadership style fosters psychological safety, allowing employees to engage in creative problem-solving without fear of failure. Endang Suswanti (2018) emphasizes that entrepreneurial leadership plays a significant role in enhancing employee performance through increased commitment and motivation. Leaders who demonstrate entrepreneurial behavior are more likely to empower employees, recognize their contributions, and support their professional development. In service-oriented industries such as tourism, entrepreneurial leadership is essential for maintaining service excellence and organizational competitiveness.

Employee Competence

Employee competence refers to the set of underlying characteristics that enable individuals to perform their jobs effectively and efficiently. Competence encompasses a combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and personal traits that influence how employees approach their work and respond to challenges. Competence is not static; rather, it develops through education, training, experience, and continuous learning. Spencer and Spencer (2012) define competence as an individual's underlying characteristics that are causally related to effective or superior performance in a job. These characteristics include motives, traits, self-concept, knowledge, and skills. This definition highlights that competence extends beyond technical abilities and includes psychological and behavioral aspects that shape employee performance. Mathis and Jackson (2011) state that performance affects the extent to which employees contribute to the organization, which includes the following aspects:

1. Quantity of output
2. Quality of output
3. Timeliness of results
4. Attendance at the workplace
5. Ability to work cooperatively

In organizational settings, competence plays a crucial role in determining how well employees can adapt to job demands and organizational changes. Competent employees are better equipped to solve problems, make decisions, and perform tasks accurately. In the tourism and travel industry, employee competence is particularly important due to the need for service orientation, communication skills, cultural sensitivity, and flexibility in responding to customer needs. Competence also serves as a foundation for employee confidence and motivation. Employees who possess adequate competencies tend to feel more capable and engaged in their work, which positively influences their performance. Conversely, a mismatch between employee competence and job requirements can result in inefficiency, errors, and decreased performance. Based on the competency model proposed by Spencer and Spencer (2012), employee competence can be assessed through several indicators, including knowledge related to the job, technical and interpersonal skills, self-concept and values, personal characteristics, and motivation. These dimensions collectively determine an employee's ability to perform effectively and contribute to organizational success.

The Relationship between Leadpreneurship and Employee Competence

Entrepreneurial leadership or leadpreneurship is viewed as being closely related to employee competence, as it can encourage the development of employee competencies by providing employees with freedom to innovate and take risks. In addition, leadpreneurship offers support and space for creativity, thereby stimulating employees to explore their hidden potential and develop new skills. Research conducted by Siagian (2022) shows that leadership style is related to competence. A leadership style that is implemented through clear and firm actions toward

subordinates is able to place human resources appropriately, including task distribution, so that employees work according to their competencies. In line with Thoha (2015), regardless of the leadership style applied by a leader in an organization, the leader must be able to provide motivation, comfort, and positive change for organizational members, including changes in tasks and responsibilities that are aligned with employee competencies.

The Influence of Leadpreneurship on Performance

Entrepreneurial leadership or leadpreneurship has become a major focus in many organizations due to its significant influence on employee performance. Along with dynamic changes in the global business environment, entrepreneurship in the context of leadership is no longer limited to the creation of new businesses, but also includes the ability to encourage innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurial spirit among employees. According to Purhantara (as cited in Pinangkaan, 2022), entrepreneurial leadership explains the output of an entrepreneurial leader. Leadpreneurship develops this understanding through a perspective that involves a more sophisticated comprehension of multiple domains, enabling leaders to see the social, environmental, and economic implications of their actions.

Purhantara identifies six main dimensions of leadpreneurship:

1. Dynamic and effective leadership, which can be interpreted as an effort to instill influence rather than coercion in motivating and mobilizing others, such as employees, subordinates, and the community, so that they work in accordance with the leader's will, namely the achievement of the organization's strategic goals. In performing this leadership function, communication skills and an understanding of motivational factors are required.
2. Professional leadership, characterized by the willingness and ability to apply teamwork, creativity, innovation, and the courage to seek various alternative opportunities by taking risks.
3. Expertise and competence in one or more fields, and the ability to think intuitively as an opportunity seeker rather than merely a systemic thinker.
4. Strong entrepreneurial spirit, enabling leaders to recognize, identify, utilize, and create opportunities that generate added value.
5. Managerial capability to transform and mobilize the organization rather than maintaining the status quo, in accordance with strategic organizational planning choices.
6. Continuous change orientation, aimed at creating sustainable competitive advantage even when the organization is already well established.

Meanwhile, Karcioglu and Yucel (as cited in Pinangkaan, 2018) formulate nine main dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership (leadpreneurship), namely:

1. Team player: Leaders work together with the team rather than merely planning and controlling.
2. Vision: Having a clear future-oriented perspective as organizational direction.
3. Innovation: The ability to renew oneself and learn from experience to face competition.
4. Problem-solving: The ability to formulate and resolve problems effectively.
5. Persistence: Being resilient and not easily giving up when facing challenges.
6. Endurance: The ability to survive and continue striving under difficult conditions.
7. Risk-taking: Willingness to take risks in support of innovation.
8. Adaptability: The ability to adjust to changes within the organization.
9. Sensitivity to needs: Understanding the needs of the organization, team members, and customers through comprehensive analysis.
10. Decisiveness: The ability to take firm, disciplined, and responsible actions.

Thus, entrepreneurial leadership or leadpreneurship emphasizes that effective leaders are those who can combine leadership capability with an entrepreneurial spirit. The dimensions proposed by Karcioglu and Yucel indicate that a leadpreneur must not only possess vision and innovative ability but also resilience, adaptability, risk-taking courage, and sensitivity to organizational and environmental needs. Entrepreneurial leadership becomes a relevant approach in addressing the dynamics of modern organizations that require collaboration, creativity, decisiveness, and strong perseverance.

Research findings show that entrepreneurial leadership has a positive but insignificant effect on performance (Puwardi and Soelaiman, 2023). Entrepreneurial leadership refers to leaders who possess entrepreneurial competence, capabilities, and characteristics. In addition, leadpreneurship encourages risk-taking attitudes, exploration of new ideas, and provides autonomy and support to employees, which directly contributes to individual and collective performance. Furthermore, Pashiardis and Savvides (as cited in Selvaraja and Pihie, 2017)

demonstrate the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on school performance. Their findings indicate that successful entrepreneurial leadership is characterized by school principals acting as entrepreneurial leaders who create strong networks with parents and the surrounding community.

The Influence of Competence on Performance

Competence consists of a set of key behaviors required to perform specific roles in order to produce performance (Ruky in Sutrisno, 2018). Determining competency levels is necessary to identify whether expected performance falls into good, average, or poor categories. Employee placement that is not aligned with competence may result in difficulties in completing tasks. According to Spencer and Spencer (as cited in Wibowo, 2017), competence is an underlying characteristic of an individual that identifies ways of behaving or thinking, aligning situations, and sustaining performance over a long period of time. Spencer and Spencer (as cited in Sutrisno, 2018) further state that competence is an underlying characteristic of an individual that is related to job performance outcomes.

There are five fundamental characteristics of competence:

1. Motives, which are consistent thoughts or desires that drive actions toward specific goals.
2. Traits, which are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information.
3. Self-concept, referring to attitudes, values, and self-image.
4. Knowledge, which is information possessed in a specific field and represents a complex form of competence.
5. Skills, which are the ability to perform specific physical or mental tasks.

Competence describes what individuals do in the workplace at various levels and specifies the standards for each level, identifying the characteristics, knowledge, and skills required to perform tasks and responsibilities effectively, thereby achieving professional quality standards at work (Wibowo, 2017). Furthermore, competence reflects underlying characteristics that are closely related to individual performance effectiveness (Spencer and Spencer, 1993 in Sutrisno, 2018). Hay and McBer (as cited in Sutrisno, 2016) explain that competence is a fundamental characteristic that influences how individuals think and act and serves as the basis for responding to various situations. Competence is enduring and long-lasting, thus playing a crucial role in determining effectiveness and superior performance in specific work situations. Therefore, competence is not limited to technical skills but also includes integrated personal attributes inherent within individuals.

The Influence of Leadpreneurship and Competence on Employee Performance

Employees work with different goals and expectations, one of which is the desire to develop ideas and innovations beyond the core business of the company. Consequently, employees must make personal decisions to either remain focused on assigned tasks or pursue new ideas. In practice, not all companies are able to accommodate employee innovations, which leads some employees to realize their ideas outside the organization, either while remaining employed or after leaving the company. In this context, leadership plays a central role in managing employees and their creative ideas, ensuring that the organization not only offers services but also fulfills customer expectations. Leaders must be able to direct employees' capabilities, and leadership that strengthens entrepreneurial traits can enhance employee competence, which in turn contributes to optimal performance.

The role of leadpreneurship is reflected in leadership style and interaction with the work environment. An ideal leadership style is one that adds value to employee competence. Leaders must understand the skills, experience, personality, and motivation of each subordinate. Gupta defines entrepreneurial leadership as leadership consisting of two dimensions: scenario enactment and role enactment. In his 2004 study (as cited in Selvaraja and Pihie, 2017), Gupta explains the challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders in mobilizing organizational competencies and stakeholders, including employees, which ultimately affect performance.

Employee performance, according to Mathis and Jackson (2011), refers to what employees do or do not do. Employee performance influences the extent of their contribution to the organization, which includes:

1. Quantity of output
2. Quality of output
3. Timeliness of results
4. Attendance at the workplace
5. Ability to work cooperatively

METHOD

This study was conducted at PT Jaswita Jabar (Perseroda), a regional government-owned enterprise (BUMD) of West Java Province operating in the fields of tourism, property, and business services. The company is wholly owned by the West Java Provincial Government. On November 10, 2017, PT Jaswita Jabar officially changed its legal status from a regional company into a limited liability company (Perseroan Daerah), based on West Java Provincial Regulation Number 11 of 2017 and the Decree of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia. The company’s vision is to become the largest and most trusted property and tourism company in West Java by 2025, with core business areas covering property, tourism, and services. The research employed a quantitative approach with a verificative method to examine the influence of entrepreneurial leadership (leadpreneurship) and competence on employee performance at PT Jaswita Jabar. The population of this study consisted of 133 permanent employees, with 75 employees selected as the research sample. Data were collected through literature study and field research, including observation, interviews, and questionnaires. To ensure the quality of the research instrument, validity and reliability tests were conducted, followed by data analysis using classical assumption testing procedures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

Table 1. Validity Test Results of Leadpreneurship Variable (X1)

Item Number	r-count	r-table	Description	Item Number	r-count	r-table	Description
1	0.747	0.306	Valid	6	0.669	0.306	Valid
2	0.823	0.306	Valid	7	0.760	0.306	Valid
3	0.633	0.306	Valid	8	0.869	0.306	Valid
4	0.795	0.306	Valid	9	0.813	0.306	Valid
5	0.656	0.306	Valid	10	0.750	0.306	Valid

Based on Table 1, all items of the leadpreneurship variable have r-count values greater than the r-table value (0.306). This indicates that all statement items are valid and suitable for use as research measurement instruments.

Table 2. Validity Test Results of Competency Variable (X2)

Item Number	r-count	r-table	Remark	Item Number	r-count	r-table	Remark
1	0.746	0.306	Valid	9	0.674	0.306	Valid
2	0.730	0.306	Valid	10	0.621	0.306	Valid
3	0.667	0.306	Valid	11	0.770	0.306	Valid
4	0.846	0.306	Valid	12	0.670	0.306	Valid
5	0.751	0.306	Valid	13	0.810	0.306	Valid
6	0.594	0.306	Valid	14	0.801	0.306	Valid
7	0.710	0.306	Valid	15	0.787	0.306	Valid
8	0.821	0.306	Valid				

Based on Table 2, all competency (X2) items have r-count values greater than the r-table value of 0.306. This indicates that all statements measuring the competency variable are valid and appropriate for use in further analysis.

Table 3. Validity Test Results of Performance Variable (Y)

Item Number	r-count	r-table	Remark	Item Number	r-count	r-table	Remark
1	0.915	0.306	Valid	7	0.625	0.306	Valid
2	0.811	0.306	Valid	8	0.583	0.306	Valid
3	0.769	0.306	Valid	9	0.604	0.306	Valid
4	0.678	0.306	Valid	10	0.815	0.306	Valid
5	0.740	0.306	Valid	11	0.665	0.306	Valid
6	0.578	0.306	Valid				

Based on Table 3, all performance (Y) items have r-count values higher than the r-table value of 0.306. Therefore, all statements measuring the performance variable are valid and suitable for use as research instruments in further analysis.

Reliability Test

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Reliability Coefficient	Remark
1	Leadpreneurship	0.910	Reliable
2	Competence	0.944	Reliable
3	Performance	0.914	Reliable

Based on Table 4, all variables have reliability coefficients greater than 0.600. This indicates that all measurement items are reliable and consistently measure each variable, making the research instruments dependable for further analysis.

Normality Test

Tabel 4. Normality Test Result
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Leadpreneurship	Kompetensi	Kinerja
N		75	75	75
Normal Parameters^{a,b}	Mean	26.292	39.656	28.205
	Std. Deviation	4.427	6.420	4.981
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.067	0.086	0.050
	Positive	0.048	0.074	0.034
	Negative	-0.067	-0.086	-0.050
Test Statistic		0.067	0.086	0.050
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}	.200 ^{c,d}	.200 ^{c,d}

Based on Table 4, all variables have significance values of 0.200, which are greater than 0.05. This indicates that the data for Leadpreneurship (X1), Competence (X2), and Performance (Y) are normally distributed.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test Result
Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.805 ^a	0.649	0.639	2.992963	1.806

Based on Table 5, the Durbin–Watson (DW) value falls within the range $1.680 < 1.806 < 2.320$. This indicates that there is no positive or negative autocorrelation in the data.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Figure 1. Heteroskedasticity Test

Based on Figure 1, the data points are scattered around the zero axis and do not form a specific pattern. This indicates that the regression model does not exhibit heteroskedasticity.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Leadpreneurship	0.697	1.435
	Kompetensi	0.697	1.435

Based on Table 6, there is no multicollinearity in the regression model. All independent variables have tolerance values of 0.697 (greater than 0.10) and VIF values of 1.435 (less than 10), indicating that the model is free from multicollinearity issues.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	Leadpreneurship	0.606	0.094	0.539	6.436	0.000
	Kompetensi	0.288	0.065	0.372	4.443	0.000

Based on the SPSS output, the multiple linear regression model is formulated as:

$$Y = 0.835 + 0.606 X_1 + 0.288 X_2$$

The interpretation of the regression model is as follows:

1. When leadpreneurship (X_1) and competence (X_2) are zero, employee performance (Y) has a constant value of 0.835.
2. An increase of one unit in leadpreneurship (X_1) will increase employee performance (Y) by 0.606, assuming competence (X_2) remains constant.
3. An increase of one unit in competence (X_2) will increase employee performance (Y) by 0.288, assuming leadpreneurship (X_1) remains constant.
4. Leadpreneurship (X_1) has a greater influence on employee performance compared to competence (X_2).

F-Test (Simultaneous)

Based on the SPSS output, the calculated F-value is 66.484, which is greater than the F-table value of 1.993. In addition, the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, indicating that leadpreneurship (X_1) and competence (X_2) simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance (Y).

t-Test (Partial)

The t-test results show that leadpreneurship (X_1) has a t-value of 9.492, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.993, with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that leadpreneurship (X_1) has a significant effect on employee performance (Y). Similarly, competence (X_2) has a t-value of 7.668, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.993, with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that competence (X_2) also has a significant effect on employee performance (Y).

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination (R^2) Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.805 ^a	0.649	0.639	2.992963

Based on Table 8, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.649. This indicates that leadpreneurship (X_1) and competence (X_2) simultaneously explain 64.9% of the variation in employee performance (Y), while the remaining 35.1% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that leadpreneurship and employee competence play an important role in improving employee performance at PT. Jaswita Jabar. The multiple regression analysis shows that leadpreneurship has a stronger influence on performance compared to competence. This finding suggests that entrepreneurial leadership, which emphasizes innovation, risk-taking, adaptability, and visionary thinking, is a key driver in encouraging employees to perform better in a dynamic organizational environment. The partial test results further confirm that both leadpreneurship and competence individually have a significant effect on employee performance. Leadpreneurship enables leaders to create a supportive climate that encourages creativity and initiative, allowing employees to maximize their potential. Meanwhile, employee competence, which includes knowledge, skills, and personal attributes, contributes directly to the ability of employees to carry out their tasks effectively and efficiently. When employees are placed in roles that match their competencies, their performance outcomes tend to improve. The coefficient of determination indicates that 64.9% of employee performance is explained by leadpreneurship and competence, while the remaining percentage is influenced by other factors not examined in this study, such as motivation, organizational culture, compensation, and work environment. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of strengthening entrepreneurial leadership practices while continuously developing employee competencies to achieve optimal performance and organizational effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that leadpreneurship and employee competence have a significant influence on employee performance at PT. Jaswita Jabar. Simultaneously, both variables contribute positively to improving performance, with a determination coefficient of 64.9%, indicating a strong explanatory power of the research model. Partially, leadpreneurship has a greater effect on employee performance compared to competence, showing that entrepreneurial leadership plays a crucial role in encouraging innovation, initiative, and adaptability among employees. Competence also significantly affects performance, emphasizing the importance of knowledge, skills, and personal attributes in supporting effective work outcomes. Based on the conclusions above, it is recommended that PT. Jaswita Jabar further strengthen the implementation of leadpreneurship by encouraging leaders to foster innovation, support calculated risk-taking, and provide autonomy to employees. In addition, the company should continue to enhance employee competence through regular training, development programs, and appropriate job placement according to individual skills and expertise. Future research is suggested to include other variables such as motivation, organizational culture, compensation, or work environment to provide a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing employee performance.

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